

Evaluation and Lessons Learned from the Lidar-Assisted Control Summer Games 2024

David Schlipf^{a,b}, Simon Weich^a, Steffen Raach^b, and Feng Guo^c

^aFlensburg University of Applied Sciences

^bsowento GmbH

^cSchool of Ocean and Civil Engineering, Shanghai Jiao Tong University

E-mail: David.Schlipf@HS-Flensburg.de

Keywords: wind turbine control, lidar-assisted control, model-predictive control, wind education

1 Introduction

Wind characteristics are inherently dynamic, direction, and turbulence. Consequently, wind turbines are highly dynamic systems and must be designed to handle changes in the wind acting on the rotor. Traditional controllers react only after the wind changes have affected the wind turbine, resulting in an offset operation until the controller handles the disturbance. In contrast, lidar-assisted control (LAC) concepts use preview information of the wind to anticipate changes, hence reacting before the disturbance approaches the rotor and therefore improving the operation of the turbine.

The mission of our IEA Wind Task 52 working group is to push forward the lidar-assisted control technology and simplify its application by recommended practices, open-source tools and joined exercises. In line with our mission, we organized the LAC Summer Games 2024 to encourage students and professionals in the art of designing and deploying lidar data processing algorithms and lidar-assisted controllers [7]. The full source code, a discussion forum and the results presented here can be found at <https://github.com/IEAWindTask52/LidarAssistedControl>.

In this work, we present the evaluation of the contributions and provide lessons learned and new ideas.

2 Evaluation

The competition consisted of three different challenges, which are further detailed in this section. The overview of the results for the corresponding groups of students and professionals can be found in Table 1. More insight on the control and data processing algorithms can be found in the corresponding references.

2.1 The 30 s Sprint

This challenge was intended to trigger new control concepts and consisted of a 30 s simulation using perfect wind preview and a reduced OpenFAST model (rotor and first tower mode), see Figure 1. Simulations could be performed with the executable or within Simulink. The goal was to minimize the combined percentage of the deviation from steady states for the rotor speed and tower-base bending moment.

For the student, the first master student group from the Universidad de la República (Udelar) [6] using a multi-variable feedforward controller adjusting collective pitch and generator torque. The second Udelar master student group developed a neural network-based pitch angle prediction [1]. Further, a nonlinear model predictive controller (NMPC) with a reduced order model with two degrees of freedom was developed within a master thesis [11] at Flensburg University of Applied Sciences (FUAS). Finally, an anti-disturbance control was proposed by master students from the Ocean University of China (OUC).

For professionals, a multi-variable feedforward controller based on gray-box optimization was applied by sowento [8]. A researcher at Shanghai Jiao Tong University (SJTU) applied a NMPC modelling the gravity forces [2]. And a joint group of TECNALIA and the University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) used a combination of a NMPC and a conventional tower damper [4].

Figure 1: Results from the 30s Sprint - Students (left) and Professionals (right).

2.2 The 18 m/s Hurdles

This challenge was intended to trigger new lidar data processing techniques and consisted of six 10 min simulations using turbulent wind at 18 m/s. The goal was to get the best possible wind preview of 2 s to minimize the mean absolute error between the rotor-effective wind speed (REWS) from the wind field and a commercially available lidar. Results from seed 6 are displayed in Figure 2 (left).

For the student, a master student group from Udelar used a continuous-wave lidar with a 30 deg angle around centerline and several machine learning techniques [9]. A PhD student from the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) used a grid search algorithm to optimize the preview from a pulsed lidar with 6 beams and adjustable angles [10]. A bachelor student group from the Universidad del Norte (UniNorte) used a brute-force optimization for a continuous-wave lidar with a 15 deg angle [5].

For the professionals, a FIR filter was used together with a 30 deg continuous-wave lidar by sowento. Molas used a multi-gate algorithm and a pulsed lidar with 4 beams and optimized angles [3]. Leice used a single-gate algorithm and a pulsed lidar with 4 beams and a horizontal/vertical angle of 15/7.5 deg.

2.3 The DLC 1.2 Marathon

This challenge was intended to benchmark full concepts and consisted of a full design load case (DLC) 1.2 using 11×6 simulations of 10 min with turbulent wind. The goal was to maximize the energy produced over the lifetime of tower and blades keeping constraints, see Figure 2 (right).

For the professionals, a collective pitch feedforward controller and baseline lidar data processing using a 30 deg continuous-wave lidar was combined with a retuned feedback controller by sowento. Here, AEP were increased by 0.6%, lifetime weighted loads on tower/blades/shaft and pitch travel could be reduced by 26%/12%/7% and 35%, respectively. IAV tested a NMPC and a pulsed lidar with moving-horizon lidar data processing using pulsed lidar with 4 beam and a horizontal/vertical angle of 15 and 12.5 deg.

Figure 2: Results from 18 m/s Hurdles - Students (left) and DLC 1.2 Marathon - Professionals (right).

Table 1: Overview on Results.

30s Sprint				18m/s Hurdles				DLC 1.2 Marathon	
Students		Professionals		Students		Professionals		Professionals	
Udelar1	3.3298								
Udelar2	1.5340								
FUAS	0.5069								
OUC	0.8291								

3 Conclusions and Outlook

Ideas for the next competition will be presented in this section in addition to what we learned.

3.1 Technical and Organizational Lessons Learned

We learned from the 30s Sprint that for this specific setup, gray-box methods relying on few model assumptions and tuned via effect-based optimization are leading faster to good results compared to methods depending heavily on the aero-elastic modeling or model-free methods. Combining model-based and model-free methods (e.g. NMPC with tower damper) is also promising.

From the 18m/s Hurdles we learned that the beam angles of a lidar has a large impact on the results. For the same lidar system and for this specific setup, methods based on frequency models and methods based on machine-learning provide only slightly better results compared to well-tuned baseline methods.

From two contributions submitted to the DLC 1.2 Marathon we concluded that optimizing the feedback controller to the used cost function should be done before comparing different LAC methods.

From organizational perspective, it noticed that our challenges could be nicely integrated in project-based learning at Universities. Further, we realized that for LAC it is very challenging to have tasks which are realistic enough to be meaningful but can still be done with a reasonable amount of time.

3.2 Ideas for the Next Competition

We plan to continue with the LAC challenges in 2025. For the 30s Sprint we would like to keep the classical challenge with only two DOFs, but also add a simulation with all DOFs enabled to account for today's large, flexible blades. For the 18m/s Hurdles, we would like to use more realistic wind fields (e.g. with unfrozen turbulence or LES based) or even use real data to account for relevant real-world challenges. Finally, we plan to have a more industry-relevant cost function for the DLC 1.2 Marathon and prior to the challenge have a well tuned baseline controller.

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